

Determinism At the Root of Shannon's Entropy?

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Maximization of entropy subject to constraints may be used to obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution (and other distributions as well such as the Tsallis or uniform distributions). We argue, however, that Shannon's entropy is a mathematical procedure linked with a very specific kind of probability or lack of information based on conservation laws which are completely deterministic. A deterministic conservation law, say of the form $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$, forces one to ask whether the system distinguishes between (e_1, e_2) and (e_3, e_4) or any other (e_i, e_j) with the same sum, when they are in contact. If not, one would expect equal probability for all (e_i, e_j) pairs having the same sum. If the particles are independent (an approximation which holds for very large N), the $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_1 + e_2)$ or $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$, i.e. a number to the power $-e_i/T$. This result follows from a consideration of a deterministic conservation law. Even if one has one particle (electron) in a two level atom, one may consider interactions which interact with the particle and so the same ideas may be applied. Thus, one does not need Shannon's entropy in order to obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.

Given that one has conservation law, however, say in e_i , then the total energy must be conserved. The average energy, multiplied by N , should equal the total energy. Thus, the two constraints: $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$ hold. These admit multiple $\{ p(e_i) \}$ solutions. Why should one seek an unique solution which minimizes information linked to the constraints? We argue it is because of the decision already made based on the $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ conservation law, i.e. all (e_i, e_j) with the same sum represent the same product probability. In other words, the idea that there is a function which may be maximized (i.e. entropy) (or information minimized) follows from an a priori decision to have all (e_i, e_j) pairs (same sum) represent the same product probability (N large so independent particles). In other words, entropy maximization subject to constraints is not an independent idea, but follows from a choice one makes about a deterministic constraint equation. Thus, we argue that maximization of entropy subject to constraints is a math procedure. In fact, we have shown how entropy may be constructed from the differentials of the constraints: $G = \sum_i p(e_i) h(p(e_i))$ such that $h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ and $dG = 0 = \sum_i c_i d(\text{constraint } i)$. ((1))

The conservation law applies to two colliding particles, but if one makes the choice that any (e_i, e_j) pair has the same product probability (if they have the same sum), one may consider all N particles. In such a case, $\prod_{i=1}^N \exp(-e_i/T)$ such that $\sum_{i=1}^N e_i = E_{total}$ is the same and every macrostate with the same energy has the same probability. One may then consider a function which represents the number of ways of distributing energy among N particles and maximize it subject to $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$, but this has its roots in the deterministic 2-body collision. Thus, it is not a coincidence that factorials under Stirling's approximation yield the same result as ((1)). (In fact, they have to if the same idea of information is being applied.)

One might argue that entropy appears a priori in the first law of thermodynamics, but the first law is officially: $dE = d_1 \text{ heat} - d_1 W$, where d_1 is not an exact differential. If one has $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$, obtained above, then one knows that for an ideal gas: $E = 3/2 nRT$ and $PV = nRT$ and from these expressions, one may find an exact math differential TdS without any

considerations of a function which maximizations lack of information. The assumption has already been made in obtaining $\exp(-e_i/T)$ above.

Finally, we show that suggesting that $p(e_i)$ drop as a power law for $e_i/T \gg 1$ means that one is adding information to the MB situation. If one wishes this new distribution to represent the MB one when a certain power achieves a limiting value or $e_i/T \ll 1$, then one may also obtain the Kaniadakis and Tsallis distributions with no need for an entropy concept.

Thus, although entropy is a very convenient math tool, we argue that there are underlying physical ideas, linked in the MB case with conservation of energy (an entirely deterministic concept), which lead to the notion of maximization of entropy subject to constraints.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution

Consider an ideal gas with interacting particles. A collision in Newtonian mechanics or special relativity is deterministic in that it must conserve energy and momentum. If one focuses on energy, then:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((2))$$

One might ask: Should any (e_i, e_j) collision pair (same sum) be favored? If not, then one would expect that in a gas:

$$p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4) \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{and} \quad p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i + e_j) \quad ((3))$$

This, however, assumes independence of particles and this only holds for given energy if N is very large (approaches infinite). In such a case:

$$p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((4)) \quad (\text{i.e. the MB distribution})$$

As we have argued before, there is no need for the concept of entropy. One might argue that one may have a 2-level atom with a single electron, but it too is interacting with photons and the above ideas may be applied.

Given that one does not need entropy in the argument above, how does it arise mathematically? We note that given that one finds a unique probability above linked to a deterministic conservation law, one may immediately write:

$$\text{Sum over } i \ p(e_i) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Sum over } i \ e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave} \quad ((4))$$

In other words, one links the 2-body collision ideas to global expressions ((4)). Now many $\{p(e_i)\}$ sets satisfy ((4)), but in the considerations of the conservation law, it was stated that one wishes to have a special distribution such that all (e_i, e_j) sets with the same sum $e_i + e_j$ represent the same product probability. This means that one should have minimal information function based on the constraints. Thus, one has already a priori made this decision, i.e. argued that nature in an ideal gas does not distinguish between product probabilities of (e_i, e_j) sets for same sum

situations. The maximization of entropy subject to constraints is simply a mathematical way of expressing this idea.

We have already shown in previous notes that one may create a minimal information function:

$G = \sum_i p(e_i) h(p(e_i))$ with $h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ ((5)) such that:

$dG=0 = \sum_i c_i d(\text{constraint } i)$ ((6)) where ((4)) are the constraints.

Macrostates

Historically, one considers macrostates in a microcanonical system together with a factorial expression if one states that every distribution of E_{total} among N particles has the same weight. We argue that the deterministic $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ situation with equal product probabilities for (e_i, e_j) sets with the same sum automatically ensures that any macrostate has the same probability because:

Product $i=1, N \exp(-e_i/T)$ such that $\sum_i e_i = E_{\text{total}}$ has the same weight ((7))

One may create an a priori function:

$\ln(N! / (\text{product over } i n(e_i)!))$

Mathematically, varying $n(e_i)$ with respect to the constraints $\sum_i N p(e_i) = N$ and $N \sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{\text{total}}$, is exactly the same idea as ((6)) and so they must be mathematically the same. We have already argued that ((6)) is linked with large N and so a large N approximation of $\ln(N!)$ must reduce to ((6)), otherwise the same ideas are not being used. In fact, the same ideas are used and $\ln(n!) \approx n \ln(n)$.

First Law of Thermodynamics

Given that one may apply minimal information ideas to a deterministic energy conservation law $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$, one may directly obtain $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$. This means that:

$E = 3/2 nRT$ and $PV = nRT$ ((8)) for an ideal gas

The first law of thermodynamics states that $dE = d1Q - d1W$. Here Q is heat and W , work, but $d1$ is not an exact differential. Creating exact differentials, one has:

$dE = TdS - PdV$ ((9))

One might argue that entropy (i.e a minimal information function) exists a priori in ((9)), but actually the Sackur-Tetrode expression for S follows from ((8)). One does not need to know that Shannon's entropy exists to find it. The fact that S in ((9)) is linked to the function G in ((6)) is no

surprise because both are linked to the average energy constraint. Here one adds an extra V (volume) dependent piece.

Tsallis and Kaniadakis Cases

Given a deterministic energy conservation law and the assumption of particle independence (N very large), one finds $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$. If one wishes to have a power law tail for large e_i/T , then this represents a different physical scenario, i.e. a non-minimal information one with respect to (e_i, e_j) pairs with the same sum.

One may consider a single power for the tail and argue that if this power reaches a certain limit or $e_i/T \ll 1$, one no longer sees the effect of a power law, i.e. returns to the MB case. This idea alone is sufficient for obtaining the Tsallis and Kaniadakis distributions.

In the Tsallis case, one considers a linear approximation to $\exp(-(1-q)e_i/T)$, where q is a parameter. In such a case, one would have:

$$p(e_i) = (1 + (1-q)(-e_i/T))^{-1/(1-q)} \quad \text{such that both } q \rightarrow 1 \text{ or } e_i/T \ll 1 \text{ yields the MB distribution} \quad ((10))$$

Interestingly, mathematically the Tsallis distribution follows from ((6)) with the constraints $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^{1/q} = F$ ((11))

The Kaniadakis approach calls for a quadratic approximation to $\exp(-ke_i/T)$ for $k \rightarrow 0$ or $e_i/T \ll 1$.

$$p(e_i) = (1 - ke_i/T + \frac{1}{2} k^2 e_i^2 / T^2)^{-1/k} \quad ((12))$$

This result, however, holds in the limiting cases. One requires a result which appears “linear” in the general case because $p(e_i)$, but still yields ((12)) in the two limiting cases. This suggests:

$$p(e_i) = (\sqrt{1 + k^2 e_i^2 / T^2} - ke_i/T)^{-1/k} \quad ((13))$$

In other words, one modifies the 1 term in the Tsallis case. The point we make is that no notion of entropy is required to obtain either the Tsallis or Kaniadakis distributions.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that entropy is a very convenient mathematical measure of a lack of information, but this lack of information should appear physically in a problem. In the Maxwell-Boltzmann case it is linked with the deterministic conservation of energy equation $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ and simply indicates that the product probability for all (e_i, e_j) sets with the same sum $e_i + e_j$ is the same. To consider particles as independent (product probability) one must use the $N \rightarrow$ infinite limit. Maximization of entropy subject to constraints is no more than this statement. We also note that one may obtain the Kaniadakis and Tsallis entropies from the MB case under certain assumptions which are not linked to the idea of entropy.